

2. <https://issuu.com>
3. Turizm:nazariya va amaliyot (3-nashr).I.S.Tuxliyev, S. A. Abduxamidov. Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis instituti.
4. <https://geohistory.today>
5. <https://www.lonelyplanet.com>

THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SPHERE

Teacher, **D. F.Abdulkhayirov**
Samarkand Economy and Service institute,
"Teaching Language" department,
Norchayev Sherali Urin o'g'li
Samarkand Economy and Service
institute, Service faculty,
Group -Tourism -323
norchayevsherali2@gmail.com

Annotation: The service sector encompasses a broad range of industries that provide products and services to customers. From banking, hospitality, transportation, healthcare, and retailing, the service sector plays a key role in the global economy. One key factor that enables this sector to become successful is the ability to provide services to a diverse customer base. For this reason, the importance and prospects of learning foreign languages in the service sector cannot be overstated.

Аннотация: Сфера услуг охватывает широкий спектр отраслей, предоставляющих клиентам продукцию и услуги. Сектор услуг, начиная от банковского дела, гостиничного бизнеса, транспорта, здравоохранения и розничной торговли, играет ключевую роль в мировой экономике. Одним из ключевых факторов, который позволяет этому сектору добиться успеха, является способность предоставлять услуги разнообразной клиентской базе. По этой причине важность и перспективы изучения иностранных языков в сфере услуг невозможно переоценить.

Annotatsiya: Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi iste'molchilarga mahsulot va xizmatlarni taqdim etadigan keng doiradagi tarmoqlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Bank, mehmondo'stlik, transport, sog'liqni saqlash va chakana savdodan tortib, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi jahon iqtisodiyotida asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu sektorning muvaffaqiyatli bo'lishiga imkon beruvchi asosiy omillardan biri bu turli xil mijozlar bazasiga xizmat ko'rsatish qobiliyatidir. Shu sababli, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida chet tillarini o'rganishning ahamiyati va istiqbolini ortiqcha baholab bo'lmaydi.

Key words: service sector, foreign investments, international trade, service provider, Multilingual employees

Ключевые слова: сфера услуг, иностранные инвестиции, международная торговля, поставщик услуг, многоязычные сотрудники.

Kalit so'zlar: xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi, xorijiy investitsiyalar, xalqaro savdo, xizmat ko'rsatuvchi provayder, ko'p tilli xodimlar

The rise of globalization and the rise of international trade has made it possible for businesses to reach customers worldwide, making customer service a key factor in the success of businesses in the service sector. While English is widely considered the international language, customers from other countries have different native tongues. For this reason, the ability for service employees to understand the needs of customers and provide them with the best service possible is essential. The ability to speak a foreign language presents a range of advantages for businesses operating in the service sector. It creates trust among customers as they feel more at ease communicating in their native language. This in turn leads to positive customer relationships, ultimately leading to increased customer loyalty and higher customer satisfaction. Furthermore, speaking a foreign language allows service representatives to get the full scope of the customer's problem and provide them with a tailored solution. This leads to increased efficiency and saves time since representatives can provide customers with answers that are more accurate. In addition to improving customer service, foreign language skills can also help businesses in the service sector stay competitive by giving them access to a larger market share. It will enable them to reach new customers who may not be comfortable conducting business in English. Furthermore, being able to converse in a foreign language can provide businesses with an advantage when trading with foreign companies and instituting foreign investments. Overall, the importance of learning foreign languages in the service sector cannot be overstated. It will give businesses in the service sector the necessary skills to provide customers with the best possible service and stay competitive in the global market. Furthermore, it will enable businesses to reach a larger customer base and stay ahead of the competition by giving them access to a wider range of markets. As such, learning foreign languages should be considered essential for businesses in the service sector that want to stay competitive and ensure long-term success.

The service sector is an integral part of the global economy, with its tremendous importance to the growth and development of nations. In order to remain competitive in this fast-paced, ever-changing marketplace, service providers must possess the ability to communicate effectively with their international clients and customers. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, the need for multilingualism is

becoming more apparent. Learning a foreign language is an invaluable asset in the service sector, not just for management personnel, but also for all staff. By mastering a foreign language, service sector professionals will be better able to navigate the complexities of global markets and build meaningful relationships with international clients. In today's world, the use of foreign languages is no longer a luxury; it's a necessity for those in the service industry. As customer bases and markets expand, the ability to communicate in multiple languages is vital. Multilingual employees can bridge cultural divides, reducing the risk of miscommunication and resulting frustration. This increased clarity and understanding helps to cultivate a positive relationship between the customer and the service provider. Furthermore, learning a foreign language can open up a variety of opportunities for service providers. In international markets, customers often prefer to conduct business in their native language. Therefore, businesses that fail to provide their services in a multilingual setting may be at a disadvantage. By speaking the customer's language, companies can enjoy more streamlined operations and improved customer satisfaction. Language proficiency can also provide service providers with a competitive edge, as it can enable them to gain access to untapped markets who may have been unreachable or inaccessible before. In addition, multilingual employees can better provide assistance on a technical level. As technology has changed the way services are delivered, employees must be equipped to deal with complex issues that arise in a global setting. By being able to interpret customer inquiries in their native language, professionals in the service sector are better able to respond and resolve issues with a greater level of accuracy.

Effects of Language, Culture and their Integrity

The acquisition of a foreign language is not just about learning grammar and vocabulary, but also about understanding the culture of the language. Languages are shaped in large part by the culture and the environment in which it is spoken. Language acquisition can be seen as a window into that culture and the way of life of its native speakers. Therefore, understanding a language can help one understand the culture and the values associated with it. Additionally, language is closely associated with identity. Language shapes the way a person perceives the world and how others perceive them. It is also an essential way of preserving cultural heritage. Therefore, language acquisition should not only be seen as a way of gaining a new skill, but as a way of connecting to one's cultural identity. The importance of learning a foreign language in the service sector is not limited to the corporate environment. Government organizations, non-profits, and other service-oriented institutions can also benefit from language proficiency. In an age when international cooperation and collaboration is essential for economic growth, having multilingual staff can be a huge asset in facilitating communication between governments and citizens.

Ultimately, learning a foreign language has become a requisite in the service sector. Those in the industry must stay ahead of the curve and develop their language skills in order to remain competitive in the global marketplace. Additionally, being able to effectively communicate in multiple languages can not only improve customer satisfaction, but also open up avenues for further technological advancement and international collaboration. As the service sector continues to evolve, increased multilingualism is sure to remain a valuable asset and one that cannot be overlooked.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Anderson, D.N. (2019). An Introduction to Project Management, Fifth Edition. Boston, MA: Cengage Learning.
2. Harris, P. (2018). The Complete Guide to Project Management. London: Kogan Page.
3. Kerzner, H. (2017). Project Management: A Systems Approach to Planning, Scheduling, and Controlling. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.
4. Heerkens, G.R. (2015). Project Management for Engineering, Business and Technology. New York, NY: Wiley.
5. Lock, D. (2011). Project Management. Oxford, UK: Butterworth-Heinemann.
6. Mintzberg, H. (2009). Managing Projects: A Proactive Approach. Upper Saddle River, NJ: FT Press.
7. Ajayi, A. (2008). Written Project Management: Effective Techniques for Managing Projects and Programs. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
8. Kerzner, H. (2006). Project Management: A Systems Approach to Planning, Scheduling, and Controlling. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.
9. Meredith, J.R. and Mantel, S. Jr. (2005). Project Management: A Managerial Approach. New York, NY: Wiley.

НАВЫКИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ОБЩЕНИЯ

Темирова Фарангис Анваровна

Самарқанд иқтисодиёт ва сервис
институти ўқитувчиси

Абдушарифов Хадисбек Юлдаш угли

Нурмонов Махмуд Хамза угли

Самарқанд иқтисодиёт ва сервис
институти талабалари

Тел: +998930975585

Аннотация: В этой статье представлена информация о том, как быть успешным менеджером, обладающим отличными коммуникативными навыками, руководящим командой, а сотрудничество с коллегами требует постоянного обмена информацией, идеями и инструкциями.